

Research article

Traditional medicine in Inkahuasi: An ethnobotanical study

Photographs of the process of study and identification and systematization of medicinal plants.

Photograph 1: Jarua chochogon (*Salvia ochrantha Epling*)

Photograph 2: Mor-mor (*Alonsoa sp.*)

Photograph 3: Corbos (*Cronquistianthus lavandulifolius* (DC.) R. M. King & H. Rob)

Photograph 4: Perlilla (*Margyricarpus pinnatus* (Lam.) Kuntze)

Photograph 5: Garbanzo (*Duranta* sp.)

Photograph 6: Chochogón (*Salvia ochrantha* Epling)

Photograph 7: Becerro varia (*Ageratina exsertovenosa* (Klatt) R. King. & H. Rob.)

Photograph 8: Cutiquero (*Salvia revoluta* Ruiz & Pav.)

Photograph 9: Mullaca (*Pernettya prostrata* (Cav.) DC.)

Photograph 10: Lushaj (*Lochroma grandiflorum* Benth)

Photograph 11: Chamagasa (*Menthostachys tomentosa* (Benth.) Epling)

Photograph 12: Romero de campo (*Clinopodium taxifolium* (Kunth) Govaerts)

Photograph 13: Congona de monte (*Peperomia inaequalifolia* Ruiz & Pav.)